

Supplemental Table

Table S1. Subcellular location of proteins encoded by common 213 DEGs.

Subcellular Location	Number	Genes Included
Nucleus	71/213	ANGEL1,ARID1B,ASXL1,ATR,BMP2K,CCNH,CCNL1,CCNT2,CMAS,CPEB3,CSNK1A1,DCP1A,DCPS,DENND4A,DR1,EI24,ELMSAN1,ENY2,FBXO3,GADD45B,HNRNPA2B1,HNRNPD,HNRNPDL,HP1BP3,HSPA9,ID4,ING3,IVNS1ABP,KAT6A,KDM7A,KPNA1,LHPP,LPP,MAGED2,MBD5,MEIS2,MORC2,NAMPT,NFIB,NFIL3,NR1I3,NR5A2,ORC3,PDCD2,PHF5A,PHLDA1,PIN4,POLR2B,PRMT2,PRMT5,PSMB9,PTPN2,RBM3,RGCC,RNF4,SALL1,SCAF11,SETBP1,SMARCA2,SNIP1,SNRPD1,SPI1,TAF13,TAF15,TNKS2,TOX2,TSG101,XPC,ZBTB33,ZNF507,ZNF563
Extracellular region or secreted	28/213	ADAMTS1,ANTXR2,C7,CASP4,CES5A,CNDP1,DEFB1,ELN,ENTPD5,FN1,GHR,GSS,HNRNPA2B1,IGF1,IGFBP2,ITIH3,LEAP2,LECT2,LEPR,MAGED2,NAMPT,NID2,PLOD3,RNLS,SDC4,SERPINF1,THBS1,VEGFA
Endoplasmic reticulum	26/213	ACSL3,ALG8,ANGEL1,ANTXR2,C19orf12,CASP4,CRELD2,DGAT2,EI24,ENTPD5,GPAT3,HSD17B6,HYOU1,IKBIP,LDAH,LRRK2,PLOD3,PPP1R15B,PTP4A1,PTPN2,RDH12,RTN4,SDC4,THBS1,UBAC2,UGGT1
Plasma membrane	24/213	ACVR2B,ANTXR2,ARF6,ATAD1,CD36,CLTRN,CXCR1,DMD,EPHB4,FAM126B,GHR,INSR,ITGAV,LAMP2,LEPR,LPP,NT5E,PTP4A1,PTPN2,RFTN1,RTN4,SAMD5,SGCB,SLC22A1
Mitochondrion	18/213	ACAT1,ACSL3,C19orf12,CASP4,COQ5,ECHS1,FECH,HADH,HSPA9,LRRK2,NDUFB3,PPM1K,PPP6C,PRDX3,SUOX,TIMM10B,TMEM135,UQCRB
Cytoskeleton	18/213	ARPC5L,CCDC69,CEP104,CSNK1A1,DMD,DYNC1LI1,EML4,IVNS1ABP,MAP1LC3B,NR1I3,PIN4,PTP4A1,RGCC,SAC3D1,SGCB,SMTN,TPGS2,TSG101
cytosol	12/213	AMDHD1,ANGEL1,C19orf12,CASP4,DIAPH2,EIF2B2,FAM126B,GSS,MAGED2,MORC2,PDE11A,SNRPD1
Endosome	11/213	DIAPH2,HSD17B6,INSR,LAMP2,LRRK2,OPTN,PRDX3,PTP4A1,RFTN1,SNX1,TSG101
Golgi apparatus	10/213	ANGEL1,GOLGA7,LRRK2,OPTN,PRMT5,RAB26,RNF125,SNX1,TMEM167B,TNKS2
Peroxisome	5/213	ACAA1,ACSL3,ATAD1,MVK,TMEM135
Lysosome	4/213	INSR,LAMP2,LMBRD1,LRRK2

DEGs: differential expressed genes.

Supplemental Figure Legends

Fig. S1. Selected GO term heatmap and KEGG pathway map. (A) Heatmap of genes included in GO 002576: "platelet degranulation" highlights several signature genes including THBS1, IGF1, FN1, CD36 and VEGFA. (B) KEGG pathway maps of "ECM-receptor interaction". THBS1 is highlighted with red marker.

Fig. S2. Enrollment and outcomes of liver-biopsy subjects. A total of 328 subjects were initially enrolled, of which 200 meet the inclusion criteria underwent liver biopsy histological examination. Patients diagnosed with simple steatosis or cirrhosis were excluded. Subsequently, sera of 187 patients (21 normal, 37 borderline-NASH and 129 NASH) were collected for Thbs1 level detection.

